

confirmed by a direct comparison with an authentic sample.

The powdered leaves of *T. hamiltonii* were successively extracted with petroleum ether, chloroform and methanol. The combined petroleum ether and chloroform extracts on column chromatographic separation (silica gel) yielded two colourless compounds, designated as C and D. Compound-C, crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (0.02%), m.p. 138°, $[\alpha]_D - 35^\circ$ (CHCl₃), gave positive Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol and was characterised as β -sitosterol⁶ by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Compound-D, crystallised from benzene as colourless rhombic crystals (0.09%), m.p. 130°, C₂₈H₄₄O₄, M⁺ 294, gave characteristic colour reactions of pongamol⁷. From the spectral data (uv, ir, ¹H nmr, mass) and also by a direct comparison, compound-D was identified as pongamol. The ¹³C nmr spectra (90 MHz, CDCl₃) of pongamol reveal δ 180 (C=O), 184 (β , γ =O), 158.75 (C-4'), 153.81 (C-2'), 147.69 (C-6'), 144.32 (C-5'), 135.77 (C-1'), 132.14 (C-1), 128.62 (C-3'), 127.10 (C-4), 126.51 (C-2 and -6), 122.23 (C-3 and -5), 119.63 (C-5''), 107 (C- α), 105.32 (C-4'') and 61.116 (OCH₃).

The methanol extract of *T. hamiltonii* leaves, after preliminary purification gave a glycosidic fraction, which on column chromatographic purification (Sephadex-LH-20; eluent, MeOH) yielded compound-E, which was crystallised from methanol as pale yellow amorphous solid (0.11%), m.p. 189-90°, C₂₇H₃₀O₆, M⁺ 610. It gave magenta colour with Mg/HCl and responded positively to Molisch test suggesting it to be a flavonoid glycoside. Acid hydrolysis (7% methanolic H₂SO₄) of the glycoside yielded quercetin (m.p. 313°) and two sugars which were characterised as D(+)-glucose and L(-)-rhamnose by co-paper chromatography with authentic samples. From the analytical and spectral data (ir, uv, ¹H nmr, mass and ¹³C nmr) the glycoside was identified as rutin⁸, which was confirmed by a direct comparison with an authentic sample.

The powdered roots of *T. hamiltonii* were extracted successively with petroleum ether and chloroform. Elaborate column chromatography (silica gel) of the chloroform extract yielded two colourless crystalline compounds, designated as F and G. Compound-F (0.02%) was identified as pongamol. Compound-G was crystallised from chloroform as colourless needles (0.014%), m.p. 179-80°, C₁₇H₁₈O₅, M⁺ 296, ν_{\max} (KBr) 1650 (unsaturation), 1610, 1570, 1515 (aromatic ring), 1460 (C-O), 1240 (Ph-O), 1040 (furan moiety) and 940 cm⁻¹ (OCH₃O); λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 212 (4.48), 240sh (4.40), 338 (4.50) and 355 nm (4.57); it was characterised as flemichapparin-B⁹. The ¹H nmr and mass spectral fragmentation pattern of the compound was in good agreement with those reported for flemichapparin-B⁹. The ¹³C nmr spectra (90 MHz, CDCl₃) of flemichapparin-B reveal δ 55.36 (OCH₃), 65.42 (C-6), 94.0 (C-10), 97.17 (C-4), 101.36 (OCH₃O), 102.50 (C-1'), 106.31

(C-6'), 107.20 (C-7), 109.87 (C-2), 119.17 (C-7'), 120.87 (C-1), 144.75 (C-8 and -9), 145.64 (C-11'), 150.50 (C-10'), 154.94 (C-4') and 160.89 (C-3). There appears to be no report on the occurrence of flemichapparin-B in a *Tephrosia* species.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof B. Sethuram, Head of the Department, for facilities. Thanks are due to R.S.I.C., Lucknow, for pmr spectra. One of the authors (P.R.) is grateful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. "The Flavonoids", eds. J. B. HARBORNE, T. J. MABRY and H. MABRY, Academic, New York, 1975, Part 1, p. 284.
2. H. BICKEZ and H. SCHMIDT, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, **36**, 644.
3. S. N. SWAMI, S. RANGASWAMI and T. R. SESHADRI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1871.
4. P. PROKSCH and E. RODRIGUEZ, *Phytochemistry*, 1983, **22**, 2335.
5. "The Aldrich Library of NMR Spectra", O. J. Pouchert, 1983, Vol. 2, p. 297D.
6. R. J. ANDERSON, R. L. SHRINER and G. O. BURR, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 2987.
7. S. RANGASWAMI and T. R. SESHADRI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1940, 179.
8. L. HÖRHAMMER, H. WAGNER, H. G. ARNDT and H. KRAMER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1966, 567.
9. N. ADITYA CHAUDHURY and P. K. GUPTA, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, **12**, 425.

A New Flavone from *Cheilanthes farinosa* Kaulf.

K. S. MUKHERJEE*, C. K. CHAKRAVORTY,
T. P. CHATTERJEE and P. BHATTACHARJEE

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati University,
Santiniketan-731 235

Manuscript received 8 October 1987, revised 24 December 1987,
accepted 24 December 1987

IN continuation of our previous works on plant pigments^{1,2} a systematic chemical examination of *Cheilanthes farinosa*³ (*Polypodiaceae*), on which no phytochemical work seems to have been reported so far, has been undertaken. *C. farinosa* is a small tufted fern very common in the hilly regions.

The air-dried powdered whole plant (aerial parts and roots) of *C. farinosa* was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether extract was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with benzene-chloroform (1:1) mixture afforded a yellow solid, crystallised from chloroform-methanol (5:1) mixture, m.p. 145°, C₁₈H₁₆O₆ (M⁺ 328). It gave greenish blue colour with ferric chloride and gave

positive test of flavonoids with magnesium-hydrochloric acid. It was found to contain two methoxy groups as indicated by Zeisel experiment and exhibited λ_{\max} (EtOH) 270 and 348 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3400 br (bonded-OH), 1650, 1600 and 1580 cm^{-1} (chelated α,β -unsaturated C=O). These data in conjunction with the facts that the compound affords a monomethyl ether (2), $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ (M^+ 342) m.p. 105–08° on treatment with diazomethane and a dimethyl ether (3), $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6$ (M^+ 356), m.p. 95° on reaction with dimethyl sulphate suggest that the compound is dihydroxydimethoxyflavone. The ^1H nmr spectrum (90 MHz, CDCl_3) is also consistent with the above view and displayed signals due to one aromatic C-methyl at δ 2.05 (3H, s) and two aromatic methoxys at δ 3.95 (6H, s). The A-ring proton at C₆-position appeared as a singlet at δ 6.55. The B-ring protons formed a ABX pattern, characteristic of 3',4'-dioxxygenated-flavonoids⁴. The 2'-proton showed up as a doublet at δ 7.85 (J 3 Hz) while 5'- and 6'-protons appeared as a doublet at δ 7.20 (J 8.5 Hz) and a quartet at δ 7.10 (J 3 and 8.5 Hz). The remaining proton resonance was a singlet at δ 6.35 assigned to the C₈-proton.

The monomethyl derivative (2) gave positive ferric chloride colour reaction indicating the presence of a chelated hydroxyl in the compound which must be at C₈-position. The position of the other hydroxyl group was settled from uv spectral measurement. As expected for flavonoids with free hydroxyl group at C₇-position, the short wavelength band at 270 nm shifted to 285 nm in presence of sodium acetate solution⁴ locating thereby the second hydroxyl group at C₇-position. All the above observations led to formulate the compound as 8-C-methyl-5,7-dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavone (1) which appears to be new one. This structural assignment was confirmed by the isolation of veratric acid, m.p. 180–82°, and an acetophenone derivative, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ (M^+ 210), m.p. 143°, characterised as 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxy-3-methylacetophenone⁵ from spectral studies [ν_{\max} (KBr) 3300 and 1685 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.10 (3H, ArCH_3), 2.50 (3H, COCH_3), 3.90 (6H, $2 \times \text{ArOCH}_3$), 6.97 (1H, ArH)] and comparison of physical constants from the alkaline degradation of the dimethyl derivative (3) with 40% KOH.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to R.S.I.C., Madras for spectral measurements, and to U.G.C., New

Delhi for awarding a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (C.K.C.).

References

1. K. S. MUKHERJEE, P. BHATTACHARYA, R. K. MUKHERJEE and P. K. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 619.
2. K. S. MUKHERJEE, P. BHATTACHARYA, R. K. MUKHERJEE and P. K. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 130.
3. H. H. HAINES, "The Botany of Bihar and Orissa", Botanical Survey of India, Calcutta, 1961, Vol. III, p. 1253.
4. T. J. MABRY, K. R. MARKHAM and M. B. THOMAS, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoids", Springer Verlag, New York 1970, pp. 265, 48.
5. A. ROBERTSON, W. B. WHALLEY and J. YATES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3117.

6-O- β -D-Glucosylscutellarein—A Rare Flavone Glycoside from *Stereospermum suaveolens*

A. G. RAMACHANDRAN NAIR* and S. MOHANDOSS

Department of Chemistry, Pondicherry University,
 JIPMER Campus, Pondicherry-605 006

and

BERNARD VOIRIN, CHRISTINE BAYET

and

J. FAVRE-BONVIN

Laboratoire de Phytochimie, U. E. R. des Sciences de la
 Nature, 69628, Villeurbanne, France

Manuscript received 9 November 1987, revised 11 December 1987,
 accepted 22 December 1987

*STEREOSPERMUM suaveolens*¹ D.C. (Fam.: Bignoniaceae) is a large deciduous tree found throughout the moist parts of India. The roots, bark and flowers are used in native medicine² and the root extract is known to have hypoglycemic and anticancer activities. This plant contains various higher carboxylic acids, β -sitosterol in the roots, lapachol and saponins in the entire plant³ and stereolensin (6-O- β -D-glucosylluteolin) in the leaves⁴.

During the course of pyrolysis chemical ionisation mass spectral analysis of flavonoid glycosides⁵, a sample of stereolensin was found to have another glycoside with molecular weight 16 amu lower as an impurity. The re-isolation of this minor component from *S. suaveolens* and its characterisation as 5,7,4'-trihydroxy-6-O- β -D-glucosylflavone (6-O-glucosylscutellarein), a rare natural product, are presented here.

Results and Discussion

A mixture of flavone glycosides obtained from the EtOAc-soluble fraction of the aqueous ethanolic concentrate of fresh leaves of *S. suaveolens* was resolved into two homogeneous compounds